

Effects of Advanced Trauma Life Support® Training Compared to Standard Care on Mortality and Functional Outcomes in Adult Trauma Patients

General Information

Project Title

Effects of Advanced Trauma Life Support® Training Compared to Standard Care on Mortality and Functional Outcomes in Adult Trauma Patients

Project Leader

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Registration number/corresponding, date and version of the data management plan

N/A

Version

1.1

Date

2023-03-20

Description of data - reuse of existing data and/or production of new data

How will data be collected, created or reused?

The protocol and data definitions, including metadata, will be pre-defined and uploaded to clinicaltrials.gov according to the Protocol Registration Data Element Definitions.

The project codebook will comprehensively document metadata such as encompassing variable definitions, data collection procedures, and valid value ranges. Data collection will be conducted by clinical research coordinators, specifically employed for this task. They will gather data as defined in the codebook. Coordinators will employ paper-based case record forms (CRFs) for initial data collection where each participant will be assigned a unique patient ID. CRFs will be stored in accordance with local regulations at each site. An electronic data collection tool will be used to upload the data, with each site having its own unique URL. The data collection tool is accessible exclusively via VPN with two-factor authentication. Data backups will occur at least every 24 hours. Long-term data storage will take place on KI servers in Sweden. All data transfers between servers will be conducted through encrypted VPN solutions.

The codebook will be made available in a data sharing repository (e.g., GitHub or Zenodo), connected to a unique DOI. Upon the publication of the primary research findings, an anonymised version of the dataset will be released under the same DOI as the metadata. The data will be shared under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

What types of data will be created and/or collected, in terms of data format and amount/volume of data?

A pilot study for this study estimates that approximately 75 variables per patient will be collected. Sample size calculations indicate a total of 6500-7000 patients to be included. The accumulated data is anticipated to remain below 500 MB in size, consisting exclusively of tabular text data. Data storage and will be facilitated through a secure database with API access, as well as archival and processing of .csv files on secure servers.

Documentation and data quality

How will the material be documented and described, with associated metadata relating to structure, standards and format for descriptions of the content, collection method, etc.?

No specific metadata vocabulary will be used. However, we will use standard vocabulary and keywords that are commonly used in clinical and injury research as much as possible. This includes for example the collection of injuries that will be categorised using ICD-10. Metadata with details on variable collection and valid value ranges will be included in the project codebook.

How will data quality be safeguarded and documented (for example repeated measurements, validation of data input, etc.)?

Given environmental constraints, the initial data collection will be conducted on paper. Each participant will be assigned a unique ID upon inclusion. Pseudonymised data will be uploaded using an online data collection tool which incorporates the codebook and implements data validation to ensure reliable input. Moreover, critical variables will be entered twice to minimise the risk of errors. The data collection tool is accessible only over VPN with two-factor authentication.

Storage and backup

How is storage and backup of data and metadata safeguarded during the research process?

The metadata, in form of the codebook, will be openly accessible from the start of data collection. It will be hosted in an online repository to allow version handling and have a persistent DOI. The collected data is backed up at least daily and also transferred over secure VPNs to secondary project servers daily.

How is data security and controlled access to data safeguarded, in relation to the handling of sensitive data and personal data, for example?

Clinical research coordinators will use paper-based case record forms (CRFs) to collect data, assigning a unique patient ID to each participant. CRFs will be stored securely on-site in accordance with local regulations. Uploaded data will be pseudonymised, and patient IDs will only be linked to patient names and details through the CRF.

Access to the digital data requires secure VPN connections with two-factor authentication, which can only be granted by the project PI or a delegated person. To ensure the data never leaves project servers, data analysis will be conducted by granting remote work access to the pseudonymised dataset.

Legal and ethical aspects

How is data handling according to legal requirements safeguarded, e.g. in terms of handling of personal data, confidentiality and intellectual property rights?

The project PI bears overall responsibility for the integrity and security of the data. Handling of personal data occurs exclusively at each site by the local PI and clinical research coordinators. Throughout the collection process, access to digital pseudonymised data for all sites will be restricted to the project PI, data manager, and authorised personnel delegated by the project PI. Site PIs and clinical research officers will have access to data only for their respective sites.

How is correct data handling according to ethical aspects safeguarded?

Personal data will be handled in accordance with GDPR regulations and the requirements of the relevant ethical permits. We will seek ethical clearance for the study from local Institutional Review Board (IRB) committees at each study site, as well as from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. Given the reduced decisional capacity of the intended patient cohort and the nature of the intervention, obtaining patient informed consent is neither feasible nor appropriate. We will seek a waiver of informed consent from the review boards. However, we will seek consent for follow-up after discharge.

Accessibility and long-term storage

How, when and where will research data or information about data (metadata) be made accessible? Are there any conditions, embargoes and limitations on the access to and reuse of data to be considered?

The metadata, including version history, will be readily available as outlined and accessible from the start of data collection. To safeguard participant integrity, individual patient-level data will remain inaccessible until the project's completion. Upon the conclusion of the project and concurrent with the main project publication, an anonymised version of the dataset will be released under the same persistent DOI as the published metadata. Hence, our data and metadata will be accessible since a persistent identifier assigned by the repository will lead to them.

All data will be released under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

In what way is long-term storage safeguarded, and by whom? How will the selection of data for long-term storage be made?

The metadata and anonymised dataset will be made openly available for reuse. In compliance with Swedish law, all research data will be archived at KI for a minimum duration of 10 years following the project's completion. The selection of long-term storage data will be decided by the project PI in collaboration with the delegated data manager(s). The site CRFs will be archived according to local regulations. We plan to make our data reusable by assuring high data quality and providing detailed documentation and metadata to support correct interpretation. Licensing will be clearly outlined in the repository when accessing the data.

Will specific systems, software, source code or other types of services be necessary in order to understand, partake of or use/analyse data in the long term?

Data and metadata will be released in common formats, plain text CSV and HTML to allow for interoperability. The anonymised data will also be released as a software package in R. Metadata will be available in both package descriptions and in CSV format.

How will the use of unique and persistent identifiers, such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), be safeguarded?

We will create a persistent DOI by using Zenodo for the metadata, hosted in a GitHub repository. This will allow for versioning of the metadata. Once completed, the anonymised dataset will be released to the same repository and accessible by the same DOI.

Responsibility and resources

Who is responsible for data management and (possibly) supports the work with this while the research project is in progress? Who is responsible for data management, ongoing management and long-term storage after the research project has ended?

The project PI has overall responsibility for research data, including archiving. Local PIs are responsible for data handling at their respective sites. The project data manager, appointed by the project PI, will assist local PIs and other collaborators in data handling throughout the project.

What resources (costs, labour input or other) will be required for data management (including storage, back-up, provision of access and processing for long-term storage)? What resources will be needed to ensure that data fulfil

the FAIR principles?

The technical infrastructure and human resources required for the solutions described in this plan are already in place. All data will be stored on project servers with backups and long-term storage access provisions. The project data manager and PI will continuously review the plan to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles.